

A Simple L-Band Spectrum Measurement System

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Abstract

This report describes a simple system for sensitive measurement of spectrum between 1200 MHz and 1700 MHz. The system consists of a receiver in a 25 cm × 25 cm × 10 cm RF-shielded enclosure and a separate external 24 V battery. The receiver achieves 1.7 dB noise figure and records an instantaneous bandwidth of 1.8 MHz in Nyquist rate format to non-volatile storage. The system runs autonomously as soon as power is applied, following a user-defined script: External monitors, keyboards, or wireless connections are not required for field use. This report demonstrates the use of the system to acquire two signals that are difficult to capture with traditional spectrum analyzers, namely (1) distant air route surveillance radar and (2) the simplex downlink from the Iridium satellite system. The purpose of this report is demonstrate a rigorous yet simple approach to an increasingly common set of spectrum measurement requirements. Suggestions are provided for modifications to accommodate additional and more demanding requirements.

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1. Introduction

This report documents the design and performance of a simple system for measurement of radio signals and noise in L-Band. Specifications appear in Table 1. A system block diagram is shown in Figure 1. The principal components are the receiver, shown in Figure 2, and an external 24 V battery.

Tuning range	1200–1700 MHz
Noise figure	1.7 dB (135 K)
Instantaneous bandwidth	1.8 MHz (3 dB)
Native recording format	Nyquist 8-bit “I” + 8-bit “Q”
Data storage	≥ 512 GB on USB thumb drive
Control	Python on Raspberry Pi 3B+
Size (receiver only)	25 cm × 25 cm × 10 cm
Power	315 mA @ 24 VDC (7.6 W)
	18–32 VDC acceptable

Table 1. System specifications.

This system was developed to acquire signals and survey spectrum for multiple disparate research projects. Requirements were as follows:

- Best possible sensitivity consistent with other requirements.
- Negligible impact from nonlinear effects associated with signals outside the tuning range, including harmonics, intermodulation, and gain compression.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the system.

- Ability to switch between the antenna and a reference terminator as (1) a diagnostic of sensitivity and (2) a means to discriminate between legitimate and internally-generated spurious signals.
- Continuous Nyquist-rate recording for at least 30 s at a time. This is primarily to accommodate measurement of air route surveillance radars (ARSRs).
- Scriptable frequency sweeping, acquisition, and reference terminator switching.
- GPS for acquisition of precise time and location.
- Single-person-lift suitcase form factor for easy field use.
- Autonomous and headless operation: System initializes automatically when power is applied and shuts down when measurement is completed. No human intervention or remote wired or wireless control required.
- Construction entirely from existing parts left over from previous instrumentation projects and bench stock.

The resulting system is reported here both as documentation for projects subsequently using data acquired by this system, as well as a resource for others desiring to build systems meeting similar requirements. Suggestions are provided for modifications to accommodate additional or more demanding requirements.

Figure 2. Receiver. The Type-N connector on top of the enclosure is the antenna input. The black patch antenna connected to the left side of the enclosure is the GPS active antenna. The blue wire is part of a Type-J/K thermocouple attached to the reference terminator, which allows the temperature to be measured with a common low-cost digital thermometer. From left to right along the front of the receiver enclosure are: (1) LED indicating system status, (2) LED indicating status of internal 12 VDC supply, (3) Momentary contact button used to initiate unscripted microcomputer shutdown, (4) Type-BNC connector for 24 VDC input.

2. Method of Operation

The system is intended for temporary unattended operation in a field environment. A typical measurement proceeds as follows:

1. Prior to deployment, the measurement is defined as a script in the form of a plain text file on a removable USB thumb drive. In the present system, the thumb drive has 512 GB capacity, and is also used to store data acquired by the system.
2. At the measurement site, the receiver is removed from its case (Figure 3), the primary and GPS antennas are connected, and DC power is applied.
3. The microcomputer in the receiver automatically boots and launches the receiver software.
4. The receiver software finds and executes the experiment script. The script consists of a series of commands directing RF input switching, tuning and acquisition, storage of acquired data, acquisition of time and location from the GPS module, and so on. The system maintains a log file which is saved to the USB thumb drive alongside the data.
5. Once the script is completed, the microcomputer performs an orderly shutdown. Additionally, an unscripted orderly shutdown can be commanded at any time by pressing a button on the receiver enclosure (see Figure 2).
6. Acquired data and the log file is recovered from the thumb drive at the convenience of the operator.

A typical measurement script consists of the following steps:

1. Acquire time and location from the GPS module, and various other diagnostic information available from the microcomputer.
2. Tune to a specified frequency and acquire up to 30 s of Nyquist-rate data. (Presently limited by the RAM available on the microcontroller.)
3. Switch input from primary antenna to the reference terminator and acquire additional data. This provides a useful sensitivity diagnostic and facilitates identification of spurious signals (e.g., internally-generated, conducted through power distribution paths, etc.), should they be present.
4. If a frequency span larger than the instantaneous bandwidth is of interest, increment center frequency by one-half of the instantaneous bandwidth, and repeat.

Figure 3. Receiver in transport case (Harbor Freight Apache 4800).

The native format data acquired by the instrument is Nyquist-rate complex-baseband data. For most measurements motivating the development of this system, this is the preferred format for recording and storage. However there is no obstacle to using the existing microcomputer to reduce acquired data to incoherent dynamic spectra, or performing other “on the fly” analyses, prior to transfer to the USB thumb drive.

3. Design

As shown in Figure 1, the system consists of a receiver and an external 24 VDC battery. The design of the receiver is documented below. There are no requirements for the battery other than having sufficient capacity to power the receiver for the duration of the measurement. The particular battery in recent measurements with this system is assembled from four 12 V, 20 A·h lead acid golf cart-style batteries in a series-parallel configuration, which is sufficient to power the unit continuously for multiple days. A compact and lightweight alternative that has been considered, but not yet tested, is the Talentcell Model PB240A1 82 W·h lithium ion battery pack (Amazon ASIN B078T7M9HZ, US\$62).

3.1. RF Design

Most of the RF components are mounted on the lid of the receiver enclosure, as shown in Figure 4. Because parts selection was constrained to components on hand or salvaged from previous projects, and because there are multiple paths to obtaining similar RF performance, the detailed design of the “RF Front End” block in Figure 1 in this particular system is deferred to Appendix A. An RF front end design comprised from entirely new components is possible; in this case Appendix A and the performance data presented here may be a useful reference.

The RF switch selects between the antenna and reference terminator, and is of the mechanical variety. Such switches are relatively

Figure 4. RF components mounted on the lid of the enclosure. The RF switch (upper left) is mounted directly on the panel-mount Type-N RF input connector. The reference terminator appears to the lower right of the RF switch. The signal flow is generally clockwise; for details see Appendix A. The circuit board in the center is a noise generator that is left over from a previous project and is not used.

expensive, but worthwhile in this application so as to achieve the lowest possible insertion loss ($\lesssim 0.5$ dB here) and high isolation. A readily-available alternative to the switch used in this system (which is no longer available) is Mini-Circuits Model MSP2T-18-12+, which is less than US\$500 in small quantities.

The reference terminator is an ambient-temperature $50\ \Omega$ termination which serves multiple purposes: (1) It provides a means to confirm sensitivity, and (2) It is useful for confirming that recorded signals are *bona fide* signals in the RF input, and not internally-generated or conducted through power distribution. This system uses a Mini-Circuits Model STRM-50 terminator. This particular component is no longer available, but any $50\ \Omega$ termination rated to at least 2 GHz with low return loss could be used.

The gain of the RF section (including RF switch and RF front end) is shown in Figure 5. Note the smooth passband of 1.2–1.7 GHz with greater than 55 dB rejection below 850 MHz and above 2050 MHz. The passband gain slope of about -0.0125 dB/MHz is of no consequence as the instantaneous bandwidth of the SDR is < 2 MHz.

The sensitivity of the RF section (again, including the RF switch and the RF front end) is shown in Figure 6. This is quantified in terms of equivalent temperature T_R ; the passband value of 135 K corresponds to a noise figure ($1 + T_R/(290\ \text{K})$) of about 1.7 dB.

Figure 7 shows power spectral density at the output of the RF front end (input of the SDR) when the reference terminator is switched to the input of the RF front end. This result confirms that the receiver temperature is in fact much less than room temperature ($\approx 294\ \text{K}$), since the passband is clearly visible in the output. Figure 7 also confirms that internal spurious and ingress of undesired strong external signals (such as the Broadcast FM) though paths other than the RF input is negligible relative to the passband noise.

The RF section consumes about 2.4 W (200 mA at 12 V).

Figure 5. Gain of the RF section. Data below 850 MHz and above 2050 MHz are dominated by the noise floor of the measurement setup.

Figure 6. Equivalent temperature T_R of the RF section. The red line is 135 K, which is the value estimated from component values cited in Appendix A.

Figure 7. Power spectral density at the output of the RF section when the reference terminator at room temperature is switched to the input. The lower curve is the noise floor of the measurement, determined by applying the reference terminator directly to the input of the spectrum analyzer.

3.2. SDR

The system uses a single RTL-SDR Blog V3 SDR (visible in Figure 8) to tune within the passband of the RF section and output complex-baseband data to the microcomputer.

The output sample rate used in this system is scriptable but is usually 2.048 MSPS, which is close to the maximum rate of this device, yielding an instantaneous bandwidth of about 1.8 MHz (3 dB).

The SDR gain parameter is also scriptable but normally set to 22.9, from a range of available discrete values between 0.0 to 49.6. The value of 22.9 was chosen as a tradeoff between maximizing use of the available dynamic range of the digitizer (motivating higher values) and the desire to “bury” the quantization noise and internal spurious below the noise floor of the RF section (motivating lower values). At 22.9, at least 4 bits “I” and 4 bits “Q” of the output are active when the input is switched to the reference terminator at room temperature, and the maximum encodable RF input power is about -87 dBm and -82 dBm for tones at 1.2 GHz and 1.7 GHz, respectively.

It would be straightforward to dynamically increase the maximum encodable RF input by automatic gain control; in this case, monitoring output data for clipping and decreasing the gain parameter when this occurs. This is not implemented in the present system simply because it has not yet been found to be necessary.

Conversion from digital output sample values to RF input power is given by the relationship $y = gx$ where x is the mean-square SDR output (i.e., mean of $I^2 + Q^2$), y is the RF input power, and g is a conversion factor. For the gain parameter specified above, g is found to be -127.0 dBm, -123.8 dBm, and -119.9 dBm at 1296 MHz, 1500 MHz, and 1626.5 MHz, respectively. Values for other frequencies can be determined by linear interpolation or by laboratory calibration at the frequency of interest.

The 1.8 MHz bandwidth of the SDR is sufficient for the applications which motivated the development of this system; however greater instantaneous bandwidth may be necessary in other applications. One way to achieve this would be to use additional RTL-SDRs. This is simple because the microcomputer has unused USB connectors and sufficient data bandwidth and compute power to accommodate this. Alternatively, the author recommends the Analog Devices, Inc. ADALM-PLUTO SDR, which has 2 receive channels each having approximately order-of-magnitude greater instantaneous bandwidth. From an electromechanical perspective, the ADALM-PLUTO is essentially a “drop in” replacement, requiring only straightforward software changes on the microcomputer. However, an upgraded microcontroller may be necessary to handle the increased data bandwidth.

3.3. Additional RF Considerations

It should be noted that this design is vulnerable to two effects which should be considered if the best possible magnitude accuracy and sensitivity are desired. First, the gain of the RF section – and of the SDR in particular – varies slightly with changing temperature. This variation can be significant compared to the strength of persistent signals near the limit of sensitivity. The reference terminator (with temperature probe) is useful for accounting for this behavior. Second, the gain of the SDR fluctuates slightly at the beginning of an acquisition, so it is good practice to exclude the first samples of an acquisition from subsequent analysis. Discarding the first second or so of data has been found to be sufficient in experiments conducted so far.

3.4. Microcomputer & GPS

The microcomputer is a Raspberry Pi Model 3B+, shown in Figure 8. This microcomputer is more than adequate for burst-mode acquisitions without subsequent processing. Although not attempted here, gap-free continuous recording, perhaps also with on-the-fly analysis, is probably possible; if not with this device, then probably with the current top-of-line Raspberry Pi Model 5.

Figure 8. Backend. The microcomputer with GPS module is located in the upper left, mounted to the bottom of the enclosure. The SDR is located center right, also mounted to the bottom of the enclosure. DC-DC converters are located in the lower right. Fans are located upper left and upper right, oriented to move air generally from left to right.

The microcomputer runs the Linux-based “Raspberry Pi Operating System” (previously known as “Raspbian”). In field use, control is implemented using a Python script which is launched automatically on boot as a “Systemd” service. The script reads a human-readable text file on the USB thumb drive which defines the sequence of operations to be followed, so that no human intervention is required other than to apply power. The microcomputer flashes the “STATUS” LED (see Figure 2) to convey basic status information, and monitors the “SHUTDN” button, allowing the operator to initiate an orderly shutdown prior to the completion of the script.

The USB interface with the SDR is implemented using the RTL2832U Osmocom drivers, which are compiled on the microcontroller.¹ This provides the command line utility “rtl_sdr”, which facilitates easy tuning, gain setting, and burst-mode acquisition from the SDR. This utility is called as needed from the Python control script. General purpose I/O is implemented using the “gpiozero” library.

The microcontroller has Wi-Fi & Bluetooth capability, but these are disabled to reduce the possibility of creating interference. Wired ethernet is also disabled to reduce power.

Mounted to the top of the microcontroller is an Adafruit Inc. “Ultimate GPS HAT” (Product ID 2324), which consists of a GPS receiver which interfaces to the microcomputer via a serial port, and an active external GPS antenna as shown in Figures 2 and 8.² GPS is currently used solely to collect time and location for logging purposes, but is available for future use a precision time & frequency reference and for data time-stamping. The GPS HAT includes a useful through-hole prototyping area, which is used to route monitoring and control signals between the microcomputer and other parts of the system.

3.5. Power & Cooling

DC power at 24 V enters the receiver through a Type-BNC connector (see Figure 2). This facilitates the use of coaxial cable between the battery and the receiver, which is helpful in reducing ingress of external radio signals via power supply wiring.

A DC-DC converter (TOBSUN “DC 24V to DC 12V 10A 120W Step Down Buck Converter”, Amazon ASIN B07V6X6L89) is used

¹An excellent reference for this is the *RTL-SDR for Linux Quick-Start Guide*, available online at <https://ranous.wordpress.com/rtl-sdr4linux/>.

²“HAT” is an acronym for “Hardware Attached on Top”.

to convert 24 VDC from the battery to regulated 12 V for additional filtering and distribution via the printed circuit board visible in the top left of Figure 8. The RF switch, RF front end, and fans are powered from this circuit board.

The fans are ANVISION 40 mm × 10 mm DC brushless units (Amazon ASIN B0711FVD48), and are used to ensure that the microcomputer does not overheat. The fan apertures are covered in a fine wire mesh to limit the potential for interference passing into or out of the receiver enclosure.

A separate DC-DC converter (PlusRoc “Waterproof 12V/24V to 5V Converter DC-DC Step Down Module”, Amazon ASIN B09DGF24W) is used to convert 24 VDC from the battery to 5 V for the microcontroller+GPS assembly via a micro-USB connector on the microcomputer.

4. Demonstration: Radar

Radars of the U.S. Air Route Surveillance System (ARSR) operate at geographically-distributed sites covering the U.S. and transmit at various frequencies between 1.215 GHz and 1.400 GHz. ARSR emissions have sinc-like spectrum which is on the order of about 1 MHz wide. These emissions are difficult to detect because (1) they are relatively weak because they are typically 10s to 100s of km distant and received at ground level, and (2) the transmit antenna has an azimuthal beamwidth of about 1.5° and rotates 5 times per minute, so that any given azimuth from the transmitter is fully illuminated only for about 50 ms out of 12 s. Thus, measurements of these signals require dwelling on channels on the order of about 1 MHz wide for at least 12 s to capture one pass of the beam. The system presented in this report is well-suited to this task.

The data presented in this section were obtained from a pilot survey searching for ARSR signals, conducted as follows: (1) Step through center frequencies in 1 MHz increments (about 50% overlap), (2) observe for 13 s (guarantees that a least one pass of the beam is observed), (3) observe the reference terminator for 1 s (not strictly necessary at each step, but useful for reasons addressed earlier), and (4) save the raw data at each step. This is roughly 55 MB per step, and about 10 GB to make one pass through the entire 1.215–1.400 GHz band.

The pilot survey employed a 12 cm monopole antenna connected directly to the receiver’s RF input connector, with a circular aluminum baking sheet of 46 cm diameter resting on the receiver to serve as a ground plane. Although the impedance match between antenna and receiver over 1.215–1.400 GHz is horrible, this particular scheme is convenient and adequate for the pilot survey from which the data presented here was extracted.

Figure 9 shows an example detection. Figure 9(a) shows a pass of the beam at about 0.95 s, followed by another pass at 12.95 s (the latter just barely visible in the total power plot). The emission is not apparent in the integrated spectrum, because the duty cycle of the emission is very low. The tone at the center frequency is due to the uncorrected I-Q imbalance of the SDR, which is of no consequence for the analysis reported here.

Comparison to the reference terminator (Figure 9(b)) confirms that this is not internally generated, and that the system temperature (receiver temperature + noise received through the antenna) is less than the physical temperature of the reference terminator (about 294 K) by the expected amount.

Figure 10(a) shows that the detection is consistent with an ARSR beam sweeping in azimuth over the receiver location. In Figure 10(b), the data is reprocessed to a time resolution of 125 μ s, revealing that the signal is comprised of short pulses and subsequently increasing the signal-to-noise ratio by about 8 dB.

5. Demonstration: Iridium

The Iridium satellite constellation is comprised of about 70 satellites in low Earth orbit. These satellites are readily identified by their emis-

sions in the simplex downlink channels around 1.626 GHz. These emissions consist of bursts of length about 20 ms comprised of a pilot tone followed by pulse-shaped BPSK- and QPSK-modulated data. The tone bandwidth of each burst is about 31.5 kHz.

The data presented in this section were acquired using a small (palm-sized) commercially-available log-periodic dipole array antenna implemented on a FR4 printed circuit board, connected to the receiver using a short section of RG-58 coaxial cable. In this case the impedance match is relatively good, however the antenna is somewhat lossy, as we shall soon see.

Figure 11 shows an example acquisition. Figure 11(a) shows many bursts over the 10 s acquisition. Note that the integrated spectrum plot clearly shows that tones consist of both a pilot tone and a pulse-shaped digital modulation. Again, the tone at the center of the passband is due to the uncorrected I-Q imbalance of the SDR, which is of no consequence for the analysis reported here.

The associated reference terminator output is shown in Figure 11(b). Note that the system temperature apparent in Figure 11(a) is now approximately equal to the physical temperature of the reference terminator (about 294 K) as seen in Figure 11(b). In this case, the primary culprit is the poor radiation efficiency of the antenna; specifically the loss (subsequently increased noise) associated with the printed circuit board and coaxial cable. Thus, if necessary, the noise floor in Figure 11(a) could be reduced by about 3 dB by using an antenna + feed line with lower loss.

A. Design of the RF Front End

The RF front end is defined as shown in Figure 1. Most of this subsystem is shown in Figure 4. The remaining component is the coaxial attenuator at the input of the SDR (see Figure 8). The components are described in stage order below:

1. **Bandpass filter:** K&L Microwave Model 4B120-1500/500-0/0. Midband insertion loss \lesssim 0.6 dB. 3 dB bandpass: 1.178–1.826 GHz. 30 dB bandpass: 0.400–2.100 GHz. *Current availability unknown.*
2. **Amplifier:** Mini-Circuits Model ZX60-1614LN-S. Gain \approx 14 dB. Noise figure \approx 0.5 dB. 50 mA @ 12V.
3. **Highpass filter:** Anthony RF Model AHP 1200-1800-4SSI. Midband insertion loss \lesssim 0.6 dB. 3 dB cutoff: 1.117 GHz. 30 dB cutoff: 0.935 GHz. *Current availability unknown.*
4. **Amplifier:** Mini-Circuits Model ZX60-1614LN-S. (same as Stage 2).
5. **Bandpass filter:** Mini-Circuits Model ZX75BP-1500-S+. Midband insertion loss \lesssim 0.8 dB. 3 dB bandpass: 1.122–1.770 GHz. 30 dB bandpass: 0.074–2.083 GHz.
6. **Amplifier:** Mini-Circuits Model ZJL-3G. Gain \approx 20 dB. Noise figure \approx 2.8 dB. 45 mA @ 12V.
7. **Attenuator:** Mini-Circuits Model BW-S6W2+. Insertion loss: 6 dB.

The 6 dB attenuator between the final amplifier stage and the SDR is included to mitigate the effect of the impedance mismatch between the 50 Ω system impedance and the input of the SDR, which is about 75 Ω .

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Figure 9. Detection of a radar at about 1303 MHz. In each subfigure, the left panel is dynamic spectrum at $1 \text{ kHz} \times 1 \text{ ms}$ resolution, the upper right panel is dynamic spectrum averaged over time, and the lower right is dynamic spectrum averaged over frequency. All values are in arbitrary units of power density.

Figure 10. The total power data of Figure 9(a), shown with increased zoom in the time domain.

Figure 11. Detection of Iridium bursts at about 1.626 GHz. In each subfigure, the left panel is dynamic spectrum at $1 \text{ kHz} \times 1 \text{ ms}$ resolution, the upper right panel is dynamic spectrum averaged over time, and the lower right is dynamic spectrum averaged over frequency. All values are in arbitrary units of power density.